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Review Article

Car-T Cell Therapy: A Review

Patil Bhavesh*, Sayyed A. Kirmani, Kawade R .M.

Nandkumar Shinde College Of Pharmacy, Aghur, Vaijapur 423701

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ABSTRACT

It has just been determined that cancer is the primary cause of death globally. Numerous traditional remedies as well as cytotoxic immunotherapies have been created and introduced to the market. A promising immunotherapy that targets tumours at both the cellular and genetic levels is required, given the complicated behaviour of tumours and the involvement of several genetic and cellular components involved in tumorigenesis and metastasis. One innovative therapeutic T cell engineering technique that has gained traction is chimeric antigen receptor (CAR) Chimeric Antigen Receptor - T cell therapy. Studies on CAR-T cell design are still ongoing in response to these problems, with the goal of achieving higher therapeutic efficacy and safety. It is anticipated that CAR-T cell therapy will play a significant role in cancer treatment in the future and could offer novel concepts and approaches for tailored immunotherapy. The current study offers a thorough summary of the fundamentals, therapeutic efficacy, clinical applications, and difficulties associated with CAR-T cell treatment.

INTRODUCTION

Mimicking the intricacy of the native T cell receptor (TCR) structure, ions, such as recognition, co-stimulation, and activation, in various chains of a receptor molecule. Normally, T cells can be activated and proliferated without the need for costimulation. However, during the establishment of CAR T cells, the presence of costimulatory molecules is necessary for T cell activation and proliferation. These molecules also aid in the creation of CAR T cell cytokines. The

plan is to integrate scfv fragments into the hinge region, which divides scfv from the cell membrane, to create an engineered chimeric receptor for T cells. When scfv is exposed to other tiny functional molecules on the cell surface, it increases. As a customised approach to cancer immunotherapy, CAR-T cell therapy has attracted attention in the field of cancer treatment. It functions by modifying a patient's immune system to enable it to identify, combat, and eradicate cancer cells. CAR-T cells are a unique subset of T

*Corresponding Author: Patil Bhavesh

Address: Nandkumar Shinde College Of Pharmacy, Aghur, Vaijapur 423701.

Email : patilbhavesh661@gmail.com

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cells within the immune system that have undergone genetic engineering to express certain antigen receptors and to efficiently identify and eliminate cancer cells. The antigen specificity of CAR-T cells might be compromised by tumour cells that express different antigens or lack specific antigens. Autologous T cells are extracted from the patient's peripheral blood, given increased specificity and killing efficacy against the patient's

cancer cells, and then re injected into the host, where they will help clear the tumour. This procedure is known as chimeric antigen receptor (CAR) T cell therapy. This is accomplished by genetically modifying the T cells to express the CAR, a receptor designed to identify a specific antigen present in the patient's cancer cells and trigger the proliferation and cytotoxic capacity of CAR T cells upon recognition.

Fig :- Adoptive Car T Cell Therapy

➤ **How Do Car T Cells Kills?**

It is generally accepted that normal T cell receptor (TCR) signalling and the activation and killing mechanisms of CAR T cells are rather comparable. However, new research continues to highlight recently discovered differences. For instance, lytic action is accelerated and effector–target dissociation kinetics are impacted by the disordered protein pattern in CAR T cell immunological synapses compared to normal T cell. The antigen is one of the most crucial aspects of CAR-T cell design. Antigens linked to tumours or tumor-specific antigens that are expressed more frequently on the surface of cancer cells or only on tumour cells are typically the targets of CAR-T cell treatments. An intracellular signalling cascade is initiated when CAR-T cells recognise the target

antigen and activate CAR signalling domains such as CD3 ζ . An intracellular signalling cascade is initiated when CAR-T cells recognise the target antigen and activate CAR signalling domains such as CD3 ζ . This process is similar to the activation of a normal T-cell receptor that binds antigens. The activated CAR-T cells then eliminate cancer cells that express the target antigen in a variety of ways, including: i) Direct cytotoxin release, in which the cells directly target enzymes that cause cancer cell lysis and apoptosis and produce cytotoxins such as perforin. ii) immune cell alliance, whereby activated CAR-T cells can recruit and activate natural killer (NK) cells, macrophages, and other immune cells to form an immune cell alliance that will cooperate to attack cancer cells.

Fig :-Schematics of T cell and CAR T cell killing mechanisms

➤ **Currently Available Car T Cell Therapies :**

Of all the ACTs, CAR T cell therapy is the only one that has been approved for commercialisation by the FDA (Food and Drug Administration) or the EMA (European Medicines Agency). Its six products are approved for use in both the USA and Europe, and they can be used to treat seven different B cell malignancies. The majority of licensed products target and eliminate cells that exhibit the pan-B cell marker using anti-CD19 CAR T cells, and the outcomes have been very

striking. The two primary explanations for the remarkable efficacy of this targeted therapies are as follows:- (1)CD19 expression is both quite limited to, and ubiquitous in, B cells; therefore, its targeting avoids toxicity to other tissues while assuring the targeting of malignant B cells.(2)As the anti-CD19 CAR T cells target all B cells in the patient’s body, the therapies will frequently cause B cell aplasia and consequent hypogammaglobulinemia.

Commercial Name	Product Name	Manufacturer	Applications
Yescarta	Axicabtagene ciloleuced (anti-CD19)	Kite Pharma, Inc. (Los angeles, USA)	LBCL HGBCL PMBCL FL
Kymriah	Tisagenlecleucel (anti-CD19)	Novartis Pharmaceutical Corporation. (Basel, Switzerland)	LBCL HGBCL FL B-ALL
Breyanzi	Lisocabtagene maraleucel (anti-CD19)	Juno the rapeutics, Inc. (Bristol-Meyers Squibb) (Seatle ,WA, USA)	LBCL HGBCL PMBCL FL3B
Tecartus	Brexucabtagene autoleucel (anti-CD19)	Kite Pharma, Inc. (Los angeles, USA)	MCL B- ALL
Abecma	Idecabtagene vicleucel (anti-BCMA)	Celgene Corporation (Bristol-Meyers Sqibb) (Summit, NJ, USA)	MM

Fig :- List of the available CAR T cell products, available in either Europe, under the EMA

Antigens like CD20 and CD22, which have had some success in immunotherapies, are also under disquisition for possible Auto T development, along with HER2, IL13R α 2, and others. It's also worth noting that hematological malignancies have been far more targets for Auto T cell curatives than solid excrescences, incompletely due to the massive differences in excrescence stroma permissiveness. Compactly, in blood malignancy, Auto T cells are not needed to access through thick layers of extracellular matrix (ECM) to get to the excrescence cells, so access to target cells is vastly easier. Although, as of now, commercially available Auto T cell curatives are many, and thus products are well-defined formulas, one can fantasize that, in the future, they will be named or indeed custom made for each case, considering the specific characteristics of their particular illness, under the generalities of perfection drug and substantiated remedy.

➤ **What to expect from Car T Cell Therapy :**

❖ Following approval for CAR T-cell therapy, patients will receive the following medical care:-

- **Collection:** Cases at the UPMC Hillman Cancer Centre's Mario Lemieux Centre for Blood Cancers undergo leukapheresis. T lymphocytes and other white blood cells are removed from the case during this process.
- **Modification:** The manufacturing lab receives the gathered cells from our platoon, and they suffer inheritable revision to express fantastic antigen receptors (buses) on their face
- **Multiplication:** As the genetically altered T cells develop in the laboratory, they gain and come more multitudinous. It takes two to three weeks for the lab to indurate the multiplied cells and return them to the UPMC Hillman Cancer Centre.
- **Chemotherapy:** A many days before being admitted to the sanitarium for infusion, cases will admit exertion chemotherapy. This

treatment enhances the invested Auto T cells' capacity to gain.

- **Infusion and Inpatient Hospitalisation:**

Following their admission to UPMC Shadyside, cases get a single infusion of Auto T cells, which functions also to a blood transfusion, back into their rotation. After entering an infusion, cases generally remain in the sanitarium for one to two weeks so that our staff can keep a close eye out for any possible adverse goods.

- **Recovery:**

There is usually a two to three month risk/recovery period following CAR T-cell therapy. Throughout this period, patients must be continuously monitored for therapy responses and possibly dangerous side effects. The US Food and Drug Administration mandates that patients undergoing CAR T-cell therapy remain in the vicinity of UPMC Hillman Cancer Centre for the initial thirty days of their acute recuperation. Bus T cells are invested as part of the factual treatment. An intravenous line (IV) is used to administer a bus T-cell infusion, which takes five to thirty beats. During the procedure, you might have to remain in the sanitarium. A blood transfusion is analogous to the infusion procedure.

- 1) Up to their use, the CAR T cells are kept in a medical bag.
- 2) The intravenous line is connected to the bag containing CAR T cells by your cell therapy nurse.
- 3) The freshly formed cells enter your circulation.

➤ **Structure Of the Car-T Cell :-**

Because of the unmatched tunability of effector cell features (such affinity, persistence, and potency) that the CAR modular composition offers, CAR T cell therapies provide a great deal of diversity in medical applications. In reality, it is very easy to insert, modify, or remove domain-encoding sequences and create a unique CAR construct using basic plasmid editing and cloning.

Membrane-bound signalling receptors known as CARs are made up of a transmembrane domain, one or more cytoplasmic domains, and ligand-binding and spacer ectodomains. The ligand-binding domain (abbreviated LBD from here on), which is in charge of antigen recognition, makes up the outermost area. The transmembrane domain maintains the receptor membrane's attachment between the ectodomains and the cytoplasmic region, which is made up of the endodomains. Autologous T cells from patients that have been altered to express the CD19 chimeric antigen receptor (CAR) are used in CAR-T cell treatment. This helps eradicate B cells, including cancerous ones. CARs made up of five components are used in current CAR-T cell treatments. For additional information on how each component works, please refer to the diagram and text that go with it below. The extracellular receptor that attaches itself to the

specific antigen. An extracellular hinge element that increases binding affinity by offering flexibility. The antigen-recognition domain, often referred to as the external recognition area, is a distinct component of CAR-T cells that is typically made up of a scFv that recognises and binds to the target antigen. The scFv is composed of structural domains linked to CD3 ζ or other signalling domains, including CD28, 4-1BB, CD19, and OX40 domains, in addition to an antigen-binding region. Variable areas of the heavy and light chains are linked together with great specificity and affinity to form single-chain antibodies. By attaching to the antigen, the scFv presents it to T cells and triggers their antitumor response. The extremely precise recognition and killing capabilities of CAR-T cells for particular antigens can be ensured by choosing the right scFv

Fig :- Structure Of The Car T Cell

➤ **Architectural ideology of T cell engineering and CAR Design :**

The capacity of chimeric receptors to mimic the intricacy of the native T cell receptor (TCR) structure allows them to fuse or split discrete critical activities, such as recognition, co-stimulation, and activation, in separate chains of a receptor molecule. This ability makes chimeric receptors unique. Normally, T cells can be activated and proliferated without the need for costimulation. However, during the establishment

of CAR T cells, the presence of costimulatory molecules is necessary for T cell activation and proliferation. These molecules also aid in the creation of CAR T cell cytokines. The plan is to integrate scFv fragments into the hinge region, which divides scFv from the cell membrane, to create an engineered chimeric receptor for T cells.

- **First generation of CARs :-** A CD3 ζ chain serves as a crucial signal transmitter for signals from endogenous TCRs in the first-generation CAR T model. This kind of medication entered

phase – 1 clinical trials for leukaemia, lymphoma, and several other cancers, such as neuroblastoma and ovarian cancer, after a positive outcome in pre-clinical trials. In patients with B-cell lymphoma infused with α -CD20-CD3 ζ CAR T cells and several neuroblastoma patients treated with scFv-CD3 ζ CAR T cells, prolonged exposure to the tumour environment has resulted in ongoing therapeutic effects, despite the insufficient antitumor action due to the lack of activation.

- **Second generation of CARs :-** The path for second-generation CAR T cell treatment was cleared by the first-generation CARs triumph in phase 1 clinical trials. In phase I clinical studies, this CAR T cell model was developed to elicit a more effective anti-leukemic response, with complete remission rates of up to 90% in patients with recurrent B-cell. In this instance, the CD3 domain-attached 4-1BB or CD28 co-stimulatory domain was combined with the second-generation anti-CD19 T

cells. The receptor is referred to as a second-generation CAR because first-generation CARs have a CD3 ζ chain as a major transmitter of signals from endogenous TCRs, whereas second-generation CARs have a CD3 ζ chain and a single costimulatory protein.

Third generation of CARs :- All previous CARs assisted in modulating the T cell anti-cancer response and were founded on a precise strategy. Nevertheless, these were limited, with worsening attributable to antigen-negative cancer cells and lack of anticancer effect against solid tumours because of significant phenotypic heterogeneity. A new CAR strategy was created as a result of these failures. By inducing the production of transgenic immune modifiers such interleukin (IL)-12, which activates innate immune cells and enhances T cell activation to diminish antigen-negative cancer cells in the marked environment, third generation CAR was introduced to establish the tumour background.

CAR T Cell Processing :

Fig :- Simplified visualization of the steps involved in an example manufacturing process for CAR T cells

The manufacturing of CAR T cells is a multi-step, one-to-two-week-long ex vivo process which deeply affects functionality, and thus influences the outcomes of both preclinical results and therapy. Peripheral blood mononuclear cells (PBMCs) are collected and isolated to start the general production process. Leukapheresis is a kind of apheresis that automatically isolates leukocytes. Alternatively, the patient’s blood can

be drawn and separated into distinct components (e.g., using density-gradient centrifugation with Ficoll-Paque). This can be accomplished using viral or non-viral methods that introduce the CAR construct into the lymphocytes. The separated T cells must then undergo genetic alteration. This can be accomplished using viral or non-viral methods that introduce the CAR construct into the lymphocytes. The construct is often DNA-

encoded, integrating into the T cell genome to provide long-term expression. Additionally, transitory expression is possible with RNA-based designs, which can aid to enhance toxicity profiles. The most common method for producing CAR T cells is viral technique, which often uses costly lentiviral or γ -retroviral vectors with high transduction effectiveness.

➤ **Advantages of CAR Therapy over other therapies :**

The quick time intervention and single CAR T cell injection of CAR T cell therapy are its most significant advantages over other cancer therapies.

In addition, the patient just needs two to three weeks of appropriate treatment and supervision. Regarded as a “drug of the present day,” CAR T cell therapy has the potential to be effective for decades due to the cells’ long-term ability to survive in the host body and their unwavering capacity to locate and eliminate cancer cells after recurrence . Patients who have not responded well to transplantation or who relapse after receiving a transplant are currently eligible to receive CAR T cell treatment. Different types of transplants are predicted to be replaced by CAR T cell treatment.

Fig :- List of Chimeric antigen receptor Therapy Clinical Trials

Target Antigen	Type of Cancer	Clinical Trial ID	Target Antigen	Type of Cancer
CD19	BALL	NCT01044069	CD19	BALL
CD19	B-CLL	NCT00466531	CD19	B-CLL
CD19	Leukemia	NCT01416974	CD19	Leukemia
CD19	Lymphoma	NCT00586391	CD19	Lymphoma
CD20	Mantle cell leukemia/B-NHL	NCT00621452	CD20	Mantle cell leukemia/B-NHL
CD22	Non-Hodgkins Lymphoma	NCT02315612	CD22	Non-Hodgkins Lymphoma
CD133	Hepatocellular Carcinoma	NCT02541370	CD133	Hepatocellular Carcinoma
CD171	Neuroblastoma	NCT02311621	CD171	Neuroblastoma
PMSA	Prostate Cancer	NCT001140373	PMSA	Prostate Cancer
CEA	Breast Cancer	NCT00673829	CEA	Breast Cancer
CEA	Lungs Cancer	NCT00673827	CEA	Lungs Cancer
CEA	Colorectal Cancer	NCT00673322	CEA	Colorectal Cancer
HER-2	Osteosarcoma	NCT00902044	HER-2	Osteosarcoma
HER-2	Glioblastoma	NCT01109095	HER-2	Glioblastoma
CD30	Lymphoma	NCT02274584	CD30	Lymphoma
FAP	Malignant pleural Mesothelioma	NCT01722149	FAP	Malignant pleural Mesothelioma
NKGD2	Leukemia	NCT02203825	NKGD2	Leukemia
GD2	Neuroblastoma/Osteosarcoma	NCT03356795	GD2	Neuroblastoma/Osteosarcoma
Mesothelin	Pancreatic Cancer	NCT02706782	Mesothelin	Pancreatic Cancer

➤ **Conditional Expression of CAR T cells :**

Expression with conditions After being exposed to a specific stimulus, CAR T cells only express the normal CAR construct. This stimulus can take the form of a soluble ligand, but it is possible to induce the production of two different CARs in these cells: a “priming” CAR that lacks CD3 ζ and is able to induce the development of a second, “true” CAR. Since this final kind of conditional

expression CAR necessitates the presence of two antigens, it is also thought to operate as a specific kind of AND operator. The genuine CAR construct, on the other hand, is induced to express itself when the priming CAR recognises the first antigen. This allows the CAR T cell to be activated upon identification of the second antigen.

1) Switchable CARs :-

These CARs allow for the replacement of a module, specifically the LBD, as their name would seem to suggest. To do this, a CAR with an ectodomain that attaches to a modified soluble LBD via a tiny ligand is created in place of a conventional LBD. This enables the patient to get alternative LBDs and regulate the concentration of the tiny ligand, hence changing the targeting of the CARs. This tactic is especially helpful since it decreases the occurrence of antigen-escape phenomena by rerouting CAR T cell targeting towards subpopulations of cancer cells that evade the first targeting.

2) Inhibitory CARs :-

iCAR builds function as an add on for the primary CAR. In summary, upon binding to its target, an iCAR triggers inhibitory pathways which obstruct any activation signals originating from the primary CAR. Essentially, when healthy cells co-express the inhibitory antigen an antigen that, ideally, only malignant cells express and the primary CAR's cognate antigen, CAR T cells with iCARs will not be able to activate. Once more, this kind of approach lessens toxicity off-tumor. The idea of iCARs, or CARs containing an inhibitory signalling domain, is to improve the on-tumor specificity of CAR-T cell treatments. CAR/iCAR coexpressing T cells are intended to kill cancer cells but not healthy cells expressing the CAR antigen if the iCAR target antigen is substantially expressed on healthy tissue but is not expressed by cancer cells. We used a well-established reporter cell system in this work to show that iCAR constructs containing signalling domains derived from BTLA have a high efficacy. Subsequently, α CD19-iCARs were able to inhibit T cell proliferation and cytokine generation in primary human T cells.

3) Suicide CAR T cells :-

Suicide CAR T cells contain an inbuilt "off-switch," as implied by their name. For instance, they may produce a ligand-inducible caspase,

which, upon encountering the ligand, dimerises and activates, thereby instigating the death of T cells. By employing this technique, clinicians can promptly and safely stop an excessive or undesired CAR T cell response by providing the patient with the proper ligand. A dimerisation domain linked to a caspase-9 domain was encoded by the suicide gene. Mice's tumours were eradicated by T cells that expressed the anti-SLAMF7 CAR with suicide-gene construct, which precisely recognised SLAMF7 in vitro. Applying the dimerising chemical AP1903 (rimiducid) on demand destroyed T cells bearing this construct.

CONCLUSION :

Numerous B cell-associated cancers have been successfully treated using CAR-T cell therapy, a ground-breaking immunotherapy. For individuals for whom traditional therapies have not worked, CAR-T cells offer a novel treatment option by identifying and eliminating malignant cells by targeting certain antigens on the surface of tumours. Nevertheless, there are still a lot of obstacles and restrictions with CAR-T cell treatment. During treatment, severe side effects as CRS and neurotoxicity could happen. On the other hand, CAR-T cell efficacy and endurance may be restricted by immune escape mechanisms and tumour microenvironment suppression. Thus, one of the main research focusses is to significantly improve the safety, specificity, and durability of CAR-T cell treatments. It is anticipated that CAR-T cell therapy will continue to advance and be used in the future. First, there will be ongoing improvements made to the design and manufacture of CAR-T cells, including the introduction of genetically modified CAR-T cells, changeable switch systems, and bispecific CARs. Second, a broader spectrum of illnesses, including infectious diseases, autoimmune disorders, and different forms of cancer, may be treated using CAR-T cell therapy. A hinge region, a transmembrane domain, an extracellular target antigen-binding domain,

and one or more intracellular signalling domains make up the four primary parts of CARs, which are modular synthetic receptors. The treatment of several haematological cancers has been completely transformed by CAR-T cells. Nevertheless, there are still challenges, which were covered in this assessment. It is difficult to train a workforce to match the demands of this dynamic and complicated profession, and creative curriculum development is needed. 6. The function of CAR-T cells depends on antigen selection. Because of the CAR-T cells' selective pressure, tumour cells have the ability to downregulate antigens. It can be difficult to obtain CAR-T cells to migrate to and infiltrate solid tumours. CAR-T cell therapy has completely changed how solid tumours and a variety of haematological malignancies are treated. This innovative strategy uses genetically engineered T cells' ability to identify and destroy cancer cells. CAR-T cell therapy has revolutionized the way hematological malignancies are treated and offers potential for solid tumors. This therapy's potential to improve patient outcomes will be expanded by ongoing research and innovation, which will also address obstacles.

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